

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part IV,

BY UPENDRA NATH BRAHMACHARI, JNANENDRA MOHAN DAS-GUPTA
AND TARAPADA BHATTACHARJEE.

The present paper deals with certain new quinoline derivatives which, from theoretical considerations, may be of therapeutic interest.

The following are the series of compounds described in the present paper :

1. Sodium 8-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylenesulphonate (I).
2. „ 6-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylenesulphonate.
3. „ 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylenesulphonate.
4. „ 8-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylenesulphinate (II).
5. „ 6-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylenesulphinate.
6. „ 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylenesulphinate.
7. 8-Carbamidoquinoline (III).
8. 6-Carbamidoquinoline.
9. 6-Methoxy-8-carbamidoquinoline.

These have been prepared by the replacement of one hydrogen atom of the amino-group in 6-aminoquinoline, 8-aminoquinoline and 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline by (i) CH₂·SO₃Na (ii) CH₂·SO₂Na and (iii) CO·NH₂ groups. In the last instance compounds having ·NH·CO group have been obtained which play an important part in therapeutic action in compounds such as tryparsamide, urea stibamine, antimony analogue of tryparsamide, Bayer 205, Fournau 309, etc.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium 8-Aminoquinoline-N-methylenesulphonate.—A solution of 8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride (2 g.) in 5 c.c. of water, containing alcohol (2 c.c.) is treated successively with formaldehyde (1.2 c.c. of 30%) and sodium bisulphite (2 g.) freshly dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and the whole warmed on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ –1 hour. The precipitated base gradually dissolves when a reddish solution is obtained. It is then filtered and the clear filtrate concentrated on water-bath and then precipitated by means of absolute alcohol. It crystallises in long yellow needles; does not melt but dissolves readily in water to a neutral solution. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_2Na$ requires N, 12.3 per cent.).

Sodium 6-Aminoquinoline-N-methylenesulphonate.—6-Aminoquinoline hydrochloride (1.5 g.) is treated similarly with 1 c.c. of formaldehyde and sodium bisulphite (1.5 g.) in aqueous solution. The product is obtained as reddish-brown needles after precipitation with absolute alcohol. The compound does not melt. (Found: N, 12.1. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_2Na$ requires N, 12.3 per cent.).

Sodium 6-Methoxy-8-aminoquinoline-N-methylenesulphonate.—6-Methoxy-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride when treated as above gives the sodium salt of 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline-*N*-methylene-sulphonic acid. The former (1 g.) is dissolved in 5 c.c. of water and the solution is then warmed for sometime with 1 c.c. of formaldehyde solution and 3 c.c. of 40% sodium bisulphite solution. The solution after filtration yields the final product by precipitating with alcohol or acetone. It is a reddish-yellow compound, crystallising in needles which do not melt. (Found: N, 10.7. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2Na$ requires N, 10.85 per cent.).

Sodium 8-Aminoquinoline-N-methylenesulphinate.—8-Aminoquinoline dissolved in 10 c.c. of water is treated with an excess of sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate in concentrated aqueous solution and warmed on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ –1 hour. The solution is filtered and the clear filtrate precipitated by acetone or alcohol when yellow needles are obtained. The needles do not melt below 300° but dissolve readily in water. (Found: N, 13.1. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_2Na$ requires N, 13.2 per cent.).

Sodium 6-Aminoquinoline-N-methylenesulphinate.—The 6-aminoquinoline derivative is obtained in a similar way by the action of an excess of sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate preferably in presence

of alcohol (ethyl or methyl). It is a reddish-yellow compound which shows no melting point. (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_2Na$ requires N, 13.2 per cent.).

Sodium 6-Methoxy-8-aminoquinoline-N-methylenesulphinate.—6-Methoxy-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride (1 g.) is dissolved in 3 c.c. of water and 1 c.c. of alcohol. Approximately 2 g. of sodium formaldehyde sulphonylate in concentrated aqueous solution are added and the mixture warmed for sometime. The solution after filtration and precipitation with alcohol gives the final product in a crystalline form. It does not melt below 300° . (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N_2Na$ requires N, 11.54 per cent.).

8-Carbamidoquinoline or Quinoline-8-carbamide.—This compound is obtained by heating 8-aminoquinoline and carbamide in equimolecular proportions in an oil-bath at 170° for about an hour. It is then treated with water and filtered. The precipitate is recrystallised from absolute alcohol. At the beginning we expected that we would get from this reaction a compound of the type of diquinolylcarbamide but we found after analysis that the compound was a carbamido-derivative. This compound is identical with the one obtained from 8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and potassium cyanate in the usual way. It crystallises in brownish-white microscopic needles, easily soluble in dilute acids, insoluble in ether, acetone or water. It melts with slight decomposition at 206° . (Found: N, 22.2. $C_{10}H_9ON_3$ requires N, 22.4 per cent.).

6-Carbamidoquinoline.—It is prepared similarly as above, from 6-aminoquinoline and carbamide. It can also be obtained from 6-aminoquinoline hydrochloride and potassium cyanate. It melts at 208° , easily soluble in alcohol, moderately so in acetone, and insoluble in ether or water. (Found: N, 22.1. $C_{10}H_9ON_3$ requires N, 22.4 per cent.).

6-Methoxy-8-carbamidoquinoline was obtained as above from either potassium cyanate and 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline hydrochloride or 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline and carbamide. It melts at 218° . (Found: N, 19.0. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19.3 per cent.).

Observations on toxicity, pharmacological action and therapeutic properties of the above compounds are in progress.

